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Navigating Facework: Interactional Strategies in Facebook Discourse

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Abstract:

This research investigates the pragmatic aspects of language use in Facebook posts, focusing on linguistic features, themes, communicative purpose, identity construction, and facework strategies. A mixed-methods approach was employed to analyze the posts of 40 participants, revealing fascinating findings. The study identified linguistic innovations facilitated by Facebook, including capitalization, punctuation, spelling, and abbreviation changes. These innovations align with previous research on language change on the Internet and highlight the pragmatic adaptation of linguistic forms to suit the online context. Additionally, the emergence of novel language creations and modifications reflects the creative expression enabled by Facebook, particularly among youth users. The analysis of participants' posts unveiled prominent themes such as family, friendship, emotional expression, seeking recommendations, and valuing others' opinions. These themes underscore the importance of family and relationships in Filipino culture, emphasizing the collective nature of Facebook users in this context. Moreover, assertives dominated as the primary communicative purpose on Facebook, indicating the pragmatic intentions of the participants. Student participants' lack of engagement in social and political issues suggests differing interests and knowledge levels compared to professional participants. The study also revealed the complexity of language use, as longer posts demonstrated overlapping speech acts, highlighting nuanced ways speakers convey meaning. Facebook served as an extension of participants' offline selves, allowing for identity construction through sharing personal experiences, cultural preferences, and opinions. Humor on the platform served as a positive politeness strategy, fostering social connections and group solidarity. Few instances of inappropriate behavior reflected the pragmatic notion of appropriateness in language use, emphasizing the importance of adhering to social conventions for effective communication. Consequently, a proposed code of conduct for Facebook usage aims to address these concerns.

Keywords: Facebook Discourse, Online, Strategies

Introduction:

Language is a powerful tool for individuals to express their identities, as it reveals various aspects of who they are, their social position, age, and affiliations (Coulmas, 2005, as cited in Gervasio & Karuri, 2019). Furthermore, Hozhabrossdat (2015) suggests that linguistic identities can integrate individuals into communities, "creating new ways of being" (p.198). During conversations, individuals maintain their linguistic identities while collectively creating a third space where linguistic repertoires converge or diverge based on the interaction and the positions they consciously or unconsciously adopt.

The Internet, mainly through social media platforms, has revolutionized how people work, interact, and communicate. Taking and sharing pictures, posting updates, and engaging online have become commonplace in the virtual realm. As a result, communication has undergone significant changes, giving rise to new genres, styles, and vocabularies that reshape writing practices. Crystal (2011) observes that the Internet has radically altered language usage, transforming how people appeal to and interact with their online networks. Computer-Mediated Communication (CMC) exhibits a unique blend of spoken and written language features, reflecting the hybrid nature of online communication.

The Facebook prompt "What's on Your Mind?" encourages users to share their thoughts with their social network. It allows them to construct identities, connect with specific audiences, exchange information, and engage in discussions. Users carefully consider how to appeal to their network before updating their status, particularly if they seek more likes and meaningful conversations.

The popularity of Facebook has made it a subject of research across various disciplines, as it has become a cultural and social phenomenon. Through status updates, users express their opinions, convey attitudes, shape their identities, interact with others, and strategically appeal to their Facebook networks. However, some posts on social media deviate from offline norms, including sexually suggestive content, taboo expressions, online arguments, and revealing images, especially among female users.

Although no provisions exist from the Department of Education (DepEd) regarding responsible social media use, a collaborative effort between DepEd, Facebook Philippines, and a telecommunications company in 2018 aimed to promote responsible Digital Citizenship among teachers and students in public and private schools. The program

focused on critical thinking online, providing tips for verifying online sources and fostering respect for diverse opinions (Inquirer.Net, 2018). Nonetheless, there is still a need to include such in the school curriculum.

As language evolves and expands on the Internet, language educators face challenges regarding students' inability to differentiate between formal and informal written language. Issues such as misuse of capitalization, punctuation, and uncommon abbreviations arise. Does the Internet hinder people's, especially students, language proficiency? Does it foster a sense of absolute freedom online, allowing individuals to post anything while hiding behind computer screens? Why do people share status updates?

How do individuals establish their online identities? How can language foster harmonious relationships? The researcher aims to contribute to the academic community by recommending codes of conduct for online behavior through the findings of this study. These are recommended to be integrated into the school curriculum, especially in language classes. These guidelines would outline appropriate behaviors on social media and raise awareness about the extent to which one's true self is revealed online. Additionally, teachers should be well-informed about language changes occurring on the Internet to incorporate them into writing classes, emphasizing the importance of adjusting writing style based on the context.

Objectives of the Study:

This study aimed to conduct a pragmatic analysis of Facebook posts, specifically focusing on how users effectively use language to engage and appeal to their audience.

Specifically, it seeks for answer to the following questions:

1. How are participants' status updates characterized in terms of the following linguistic features?
 - a) Code Switching and Code Mixing
 - b) Abbreviation and Acronym
 - c) Discourse Particles
 - d) Spelling
 - e) Punctuation/No Punctuation
 - f) Emoticons/Emojis
 - g) Capitalization/No Capitalization
 - h) Taboo
 - i) Hashtags
 - j) Coinage
2. How are participants' Facebook posts characterized in terms of theme categories and communicative purpose?
3. How are participants' identities established in their Facebook posts?
4. What facework strategies are utilized by participants in their posts and how are they linguistically implemented?

Literature Review:

The Social Responsibility Theory of Media allows a free press without any censorship but, at the same time, calls on the media to observe self-regulation (Galgitele, 2010). This theory emerged due to conflict between professionalism and self-regulation of the press and pressure for greater regulation of the media (Obe, 2008). The theory emphasizes freedom of the press but prioritizes media practitioners to abide by specific social standards (Obe, 2008). Establishing a code of conduct in the media contributed to the development of professionalism by promoting accuracy, truthfulness, and the dissemination of reliable information. This initiative aimed to elevate journalism standards, protect the interests of journalists and journalism as a whole, and establish consequences for any code of conduct breaches.

Michael Alexander Kirkwood Halliday's Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) Theory focuses on the functions of language; the system part of the name has to do with how these functions are organized (Fontaine, 2013). This theory, developed by Halliday in the late 1950s and early 1960s, emphasizes language as one type of semiotic system organized systematically and represents a resource for speakers to create meaning by selecting suitable options (Fontaine, 2013). In other words, SFL acknowledges that language is itself "full of resources for negotiating community – both across metafunctions and across strata" (Martin, 2010, p. 24). Halliday argues that language structure assumes a less prominent role since it is seen as the outward form taken by systemic choices and not as the defining characteristic of language. Structure, however, is still necessary to express function.

Research Method:

This section describes the components of the study which relate to the research methodology, such as the research design, participants, research instrument, data gathering procedure, data analysis procedure, statistical treatment, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

Cognizant of the primary objective of the study – i.e., to conduct a pragmatic analysis of participants' Facebook posts and exploring how language is utilized to appeal to their audience, the descriptive research design was employed in this study. Descriptive research design involves observing and describing subjects' behavior without exerting influence (Shuttleworth, 2008). It aims to address critical questions regarding how participants' status updates are characterized in terms of specific linguistic features, how Facebook posts are characterized based on theme categories and communicative purpose, how participants establish their identities through language use on the platform, and what facework strategies they employ and how they are linguistically implemented. This research used Content Analysis in analyzing and describing quantitative and qualitative data in terms of linguistic features, themes prevalent in participants' FB posts, communicative purpose, identity construction, and facework strategies in thread interactions in each status update. Since Content Analysis could be either conceptual or relational, the researcher utilized conceptual content analysis wherein the process involves selecting a concept for examination, and the analysis entails quantifying and tallying its occurrence. The primary goal is to examine the occurrence of selected terms in the data.

Participants of the Study

A total of 40 Facebook users were included in this study. These are the researcher's Facebook friends who consistently post online and whose posts gain five likes or more and generate at least three or more comments from their Facebook friends. Twenty males and twenty females were chosen for this investigation, consisting of ten female students, ten female professionals, ten male students, and ten male professionals. Furthermore, participants were categorized according to the following: Students, whose age range is 17-21; and, Professionals, who are College Graduates whose age range is 22-50—all Facebook friends of the researcher. The selected data for this study were the participants' posts from February–March 2020. Data were collected a month after. The participants were chosen based on the following considerations: the frequency of posting on Facebook and the number of their Facebook friends, which should at least be 200, to ensure that the account is active; the length of existence of their Facebook account, which should at least be five years old or more; their consistency of updating their status, which should be at least every day, every other day, or every week; and the FB profile name which should bear the participant's actual name to ensure the authenticity of the information they disclose in their profile. During data collection, however, some participants changed their profile names. The researcher did not have control of this.

Frequency of post means that the participants update their status in the form of text, which may or may not include attachments such as photographs, memes, or videos, or shared a video link, a news link, a meme, or a shared post from another user, at least twice or more per day or each week. However, during data collection, which took place for a month, there were Facebook users (who were pre-selected) who only posted a total of 10 status updates for one month. The researcher did not have control of this. Moreover, only Facebook status updates in the form of texts; or texts with attached photographs, memes, videos, shared video links, a news link, meme, photograph, or another post, were the ones that were subjected to analysis. Posts made on "My Day" were not included in the analysis since the researcher had no access to the participants' friends' comments on them.

Data

The data for this study were the status updates on the "walls" of participants wherein friends can leave messages or write comments on these posts. These were the different posts from February 2020-March 2020. Data were collected a month after. Participants' Facebook posts were recorded and saved for a month using Facebook's status compiler app for future analysis. These posts were either in English, Hiligaynon, Cebuano, Tagalog, or a combination of any of these codes; or texts that attached links, photographs, memes, music, and videos, or posts from other Facebook users that were shared by the participants on their walls.

Due to the varying number of status updates among participants, only 20 were selected for analysis from those with more than 20 posts. Meanwhile, all the status updates from participants with fewer than 20 posts were included in the study. Facebook comments made by the FB Users' friends on their posts were likewise analyzed to determine the facework strategies used by the participants in their online interactions and how they are linguistically implemented. Due to the variability in the number of comments on each participant's posts, the analysis focused on the first ten comments that directly pertain to the participant's post. Furthermore, the analysis included the participant's and other FB friends' replies to each comment, recognizing their significance in understanding the overall conversation dynamics and communication patterns on Facebook.

Research Instruments

Coding sheets were used for the content analysis of Participants' Facebook posts: Linguistic Features (Appendix B, G), Themes Prevalent in participants' FB Posts (Appendix C, H); Communicative Purpose Based on Searle's Taxonomy of Illocutionary Acts (Appendix D, I); Identity Construction (Appendix E, J); and Facework Strategies in Thread Interaction (Appendix F, K).

Data Gathering Procedure

Forty participants were first chosen based on their frequency of posting on Facebook and the number of their Facebook friends. Twenty males and twenty females were chosen in this investigation: 10 female students, ten female professionals, and ten male and ten male professionals. Furthermore, participants were categorized according to the following: Students, whose age range is 17-21; and, Professionals, who are College Graduates, whose age range is 22-50—all Facebook friends of the researcher.

The researcher also ensured that the account has existed for five years or more, with the account holder constantly updating his or her status every day, every other day, or every week.

For a month, from February 2020—March 2020, the researcher monitored each participant's FB wall to check each post. The researcher then documented the post's date and comments on each post. The posts were saved for future analysis using Facebook's status compiler app. The participants' profiles, including their names, ages, sex, and occupation, were also noted. Only those users who use their real name or identity in their FB accounts were considered by the researcher to ensure the authenticity of the information they disclose in their profile. Following one month of monitoring participants' status updates, informed consent was subsequently obtained to uphold the ethical standards of data collection. The participants were only informed after this to preserve the authenticity of the data. Once consent was obtained, the researcher promptly explained the data collection and analysis procedures. Additionally, the researcher reassured the participants that their true identities would be kept confidential. Since the number of posts for a month varied for each participant, 20 posts were subjected to analysis from participants whose status updates were more than 20, whereas those whose status updates were less than 20 were taken as is.

After the participants gave their consent to use their respective FB statuses in data collection, their posts were scrutinized using Content Analysis, which was analyzed in terms of linguistic features, themes prevalent in participants' FB posts, communicative purpose, identity construction, and facework strategies in thread interactions in each status update. For the latter, the researcher classified the comments as either unmarked, negatively marked, or positively marked behavior. The researcher likewise considered the factors affecting these interactions online: topic, audience, text producers, and site for interaction—in this Study, Facebook. According to Powers and Knapp (2006), as cited in Vaismoradi, Turunen, and Bondas (2013), Content analysis serves as a research instrument employed to identify the existence of specific words, themes, or concepts within a given set of qualitative data, such as a text. By using such, researchers can quantify and analyze the presence, meanings, and relationships of certain words, themes, or concepts. Thus, the researcher finds this method appropriate in analyzing the themes present in the Facebook posts of the respondents, their communicative purposes, identity construction, facework strategies, linguistic features, gender similarities or differences, and interactions through comments gained by their posts. Coding sheets were later prepared for each research question. After that, the data were tabulated to determine the frequency of responses for areas/categories where needed.

Data Analysis Procedure

As for the steps the researcher took to analyze data, the researcher first identified each research question and chose samples for analysis. As mentioned earlier in this Paper, 20 status updates were subjected to analysis. The researcher analyzed each according to linguistic features, themes, communicative purpose, identity construction, and facework strategies. The data were coded into manageable content categories to focus on specific words and patterns that inform each research question. The researcher then decided on the level of analysis. For this study, words; sentences; conversational turns in each thread; and theme categories of each post were analyzed. Next, the researcher examined each status update based on each area: linguistic features, common themes, communicative purpose, identity construction, and facework strategies. Coding for the frequency of concepts appearing in the text later followed. The researcher then decided on how to distinguish among concepts. For this research, data were precisely coded as they appeared on posts. At the same time, words that imply the concept and those that are explicitly stated were likewise coded. The researcher prepared coding sheets for each participant for the linguistic features, themes, communicative purpose, and identity construction. A column indicating the posts and the area for analysis is indicated on the coding sheet. As for facework strategies, the researcher employed a classification system to categorize each post and comment as unmarked, positively marked, or negatively marked. The coding sheet included a column specifying the posts and areas designated for analysis.

Each comment associated with a post was labeled as "C." In contrast, the corresponding replies to each comment were labeled as "R." Sequential numbering was used to distinguish the first, second, third, and subsequent comments and replies. Additionally, a color-coding scheme was implemented to indicate the relationship between comments and their replies visually. Lastly, developing the rules for translating the text codes was done to keep the coding process organized and consistent.

Analysis of the Common Linguistic Features

Status updates in the form of text were analyzed to discover their standard linguistic features using the combined constructs of Hassam and Hashim (2011), Gustilo and Dino (2017), and Gustilo and Dino (2015) on the features of electronic English, namely: code switching/code mixing; abbreviation and acronym; discourse particle; punctuation/no punctuation; emoticons/emojis; capitalization/no capitalization; taboo; hashtag; coinage; and spelling. Wikström's (2014) linguistic pragmatics approach was used to further analyze hashtags' communicative function. Words were

analyzed to determine the use of code-mixing and code-switching, abbreviation, acronym, discourse particle, coinage, capitalization, non-capitalization, coinage, taboo, and spelling. Sentences were likewise analyzed to determine if usage of capitalization and non-capitalization of words at the beginning of every sentence, if punctuation marks were used to end each sentence, and the use of hashtags and emojis between, before, or after each sentence. Below is a sample analysis of linguistic features in one participant's Facebook posts. The same set of sample data was used to demonstrate the different analysis levels according to this study's specific objectives.

Analysis of Communicative Purposes of Posting on Facebook

Searle's Taxonomy of Illocutionary Acts was used to analyze participants' communicative purposes of posting on Facebook. Individual posts were read, analyzed, and interpreted and then assigned the appropriate speech act category based on the definition of each speech act. The researcher likewise considered the contextual factors that influenced the interpretation of speech acts on each post. These factors included hashtags, emojis, images, the participant's profile, Facebook features, and the overall conversation or thread surrounding the post, as all these provided a deeper understanding of the intended meaning and purpose of the post.

Shifts in Speech Acts

While analyzing participants' communicative purposes behind posting status updates on Facebook, a fascinating finding emerged regarding shifts in speech acts within specific posts. As the researcher meticulously examined each post, delving into the content of every sentence, these shifts became apparent. The units of analysis for participants' communicative purpose in this study are sentences. Since some posts consisted of more than one paragraph, the researcher carefully assessed each sentence and each section individually to determine its communicative purpose, meticulously labeling them accordingly. A double slash (//) indicated the shifts in speech acts within each sentence or paragraph.

Coding the Data

In the analysis of the Facebook posts of the participants, the researcher developed a comprehensive coding scheme covering all the essential items found in the participants' Facebook posts. The contents of the 20 Facebook posts of each participant were numerically recorded. The frequency of means was calculated for FB Status updates in text form or text forms that included attached videos, photographs, memes, video links, news links, shared FB status updates, and other users' comments on these status updates, which was to identify the frequency of occurrence of each linguistic feature, theme category, communicative purpose, the form of identity construction, and facework strategies. For problems 1, 2a, 3, and 4, which centered on the standard linguistic features present in the participants' FB posts; the themes categories; how identity is constructed online; the facework strategies utilized in each post, and how they are linguistically implemented, Content Analysis was utilized. Content analysis is a research tool used to determine the presence of certain words, themes, or concepts within some given qualitative data, such as a text (Powers and Knapp, 2006, as cited in Vaismoradi, Turunen, and Bondas, 2013).

Validity and Reliability

Validity pertains to the capacity of a test to accurately measure its intended construct (David, 2005). In this investigation, ensuring validity was crucial to collect appropriate data sets and applying precise coding procedures for analyzing the data in line with the research questions raised. The data collected, and the prepared coding sheets were presented to at least three authorities in the field of Linguistics for face and content validity. Corrections to the coding sheets were made and applied where necessary.

Statistical Treatment

This section presents the statistical tools that the researcher employed after the analysis of the Facebook posts of the participants:

For Problems 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5, which focused on the linguistic features, theme categories in the participants' FB posts; the participants' communicative purpose; identity construction, and facework strategies utilized; incidences of positively and negatively marked online behavior; and the standard linguistic features, respectively, frequency count, percentage, and rank were utilized. A code of conduct in using Facebook is proposed, which may be integrated into language classes.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher prioritized transparency by informing the participants about the upcoming study as an ethical consideration. However, to maintain the integrity and authenticity of the study's results, the researcher recorded the posts from February-March 2020 before informing the participants.

The study implemented the following measures to ensure ethical practices:

1) Participants were provided with detailed information about the study, and their consent was obtained before data analysis. The consent process occurred after the data collection phase to minimize any potential influence on the validity and authenticity of the data.

2) Participant identity and privacy were protected throughout the study. Participants' names and Facebook friends who wrote comments on each post were covered to maintain confidentiality. Moreover, Facebook friends who were tagged in the post were likewise changed by the researcher to *tagged friends. Additionally, pictures were blurred to safeguard privacy further. Participant names were not included in the coding sheet; instead, they were referred to using coded labels such as FP (Female Professional), MP (Male Professional), FS (Female Student), and MS (Male Student). Each participant was assigned a corresponding number for identification purposes.

3) The study adhered to the American Psychological Association referencing style to acknowledge the works of other authors appropriately to ensure proper recognition of external sources and promote academic integrity.

4) The study maintained high objectivity throughout discussions and analyses. Objectivity was prioritized to minimize bias and ensure the impartiality of the study's findings.

The dataset utilized in the study consisted of Facebook status updates from 40 participants, which were compiled using Facebook's Saved Items feature. It is important to note that these saved posts were only visible to the researcher, further ensuring participant privacy.

Findings and Discussion:

Table 1

Common Linguistic Features in Participants' Facebook Posts

Linguistic Features	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
<i>Capitalization</i>	580	17%	1
<i>Punctuation</i>	494	14%	2
<i>Code Switching/Code Mixing</i>	416	12%	3
<i>Emoticon/Emojis</i>	377	11%	4
<i>No Punctuation</i>	351	10%	5
<i>Discourse Particle</i>	286	8%	6
<i>No Capitalization</i>	216	6%	7
<i>Hashtag</i>	209	6%	8
<i>Abbreviation</i>	202	6%	9
<i>Acronym</i>	136	4%	10
<i>Coinage</i>	121	4%	11
<i>Spelling</i>	34	1%	12
<i>Taboo</i>	27	1%	13
TOTAL	3449	100%	

Table 1 shows the results of the linguistic features in participants' status updates, with 13 linguistic features found in participants' Facebook posts, which consists of capitalization, punctuation, code-switching/code-mixing, emoticons/emojis, no punctuation, discourse particle, no capitalization, hashtag, abbreviation, acronym, coinage, spelling, and taboo.

Table 2
Themes Categories Prevalent in Participants' Facebook Posts

Searle's Taxonomy of Illocutionary Acts	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
<i>Assertives</i>	488	51%	1
<i>Expressives</i>	197	21%	2
<i>Directives</i>	195	21%	3
<i>Declaratives</i>	34	4%	4
<i>Commissives</i>	30	3%	5
TOTAL	944	100%	

Table 2 presents a quantitative account of the themes prevalent in participants' Facebook posts. The table displays the total number of occurrences of themes in order of frequency, followed by their percentage distribution and rank. It shows the results of prevalent themes in participants' Facebook posts, which showed Personal posts as the prevalent theme identified on the participants' Facebook status, which has a total of 448 occurrences, at 67%; whereas posts about Social Issues, followed with a total of 90 occurrences, at 13.

Table 3
Participants' Communicative Purpose in Facebook Posts

Table 3 displays the total number of occurrences of speech acts in order of frequency, followed by their percentage

Theme	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Personal	448	67%	1
Social Issues	90	13%	2
Education	89	11%	3
Entertainment	46	6%	4
Politics	21	13%	5
TOTAL	694	100%	

distribution and rank. Data shows that assertives is the most common illocutionary act that participants use when posting status updates on Facebook, with 488 occurrences. Directives follow with 195 occurrences; expressives have 197; declaratives have 34, whereas commissives have 30.

Table 4
Online Identity Construction

Identity Construction	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
<i>Enumerative</i>	369	53%	1

<i>Visual</i>	248	36%	2
<i>Narrative</i>	54	8%	3
<i>Self-Labeling</i>	19	3%	4
TOTAL	690	100%	

Table 4 displays the occurrence types of identity construction in terms of frequency, followed by their percentage distribution and rank. Furthermore, data shows how participants construct their identities online through status updates. Results indicate that *enumerative* has most of the number of occurrences at 369 (53%), followed by *visual*, at 248 (36%), which implies that the majority of the participants inform their audience of the going on in their daily lives highlighting their interests, and at the same time communicating an image or persona that involves strategic use of visual cues to communicate one’s identity, values, and beliefs to others.

Table 5
Facebook Strategies Utilized by Participants in their Posts

Relational Work	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Unmarked (<i>non-polite, appropriate</i>)	5,111	70%	1
Positively Marked (<i>polite, appropriate</i>)	2, 108	29%	2
Negatively Marked (<i>impolite/rude, inappropriate</i>)	114	2%	3
TOTAL	7, 333	100%	

Table 5 shows the results of the quantitative analysis of 40 Facebook status updates and their separate comment threads, which indicates that 70% of all behavior are *unmarked (non-polite, but appropriate)*. In contrast, 29% are *positively marked (polite and appropriate)*, and only 2% are *negatively marked (impolite and inappropriate)*. Arendholz (2015), who investigated online behavior in 50 message board threads, and who likewise utilized a modified Locher and Watts (2005) Relational Work framework, found 92.3% of behavior appropriate; 85.6% are unmarked; while 7.7% are inappropriate, and where various facework strategies were utilized by participants during the online interactions.

Looking into the results of this study and that of Arendholz (2015) show how participants are trying to maintain their relationships online, especially in their interactions. While Arendholz’s study found some *flaming*, violent, passionate outbursts (Hardaker, 2010) resulting from insults, and heated, inflammatory, or incendiary comments, this study found only a few. Paralinguistic tools such as emojis and discourse particles such as *hehe* helped participants “neutralize” online interactions. Moreover, participants’ relationships with their Facebook network also contributed to less negatively marked online behavior. As previously mentioned in this Paper, a post and a comment are *marked negatively* in cases where it appears inappropriate in the eyes of the interlocutors, say, being over-polite, thus considered inappropriate. Taboo, ironic remarks, and aggressive jokes may be considered impolite and inappropriate, primarily when used between individuals who barely know each other. In this case, it will be classified under this category. Unsolicited comments in posts, or those that seem unfavorable to the user, will likewise be placed under this category. A post and a comment are *positively marked* if it is distinctly polite and appropriate. A post and a comment are *unmarked* if it is counted as appropriate, although a non-polite behavior. Mock-impolite banter understood as joking behavior, will be placed under this category. Taboo, ironic remarks, and aggressive jokes may be impolite and inappropriate. However, this area may be classified depending on the relationship of interlocutors—their familiarity, solidarity, or even a signal of intimacy.

Limitations and Further Research:

This section presents the conclusion formed from the results of this study. A set of recommendations addressed to concerned stakeholders follows.

Conclusions

Facebook has been integrated into the Filipinos’ daily lives, especially in providing them with a venue to share offline and online activities—update their network of the goings-on in their lives, share and comment on content, find like-minded others, build and maintain relationships, express themselves, and even construct identities of themselves.

Facebook has facilitated new forms of language use, including capitalization, punctuation, spelling, and abbreviation changes. These linguistic innovations support researchers' observations of language change online, showcasing new language and literacy practices. This language creativity, including changes in capitalization, punctuation, spelling, and abbreviations, highlights the pragmatic aspect of language as users adapt their linguistic forms and practices to suit the online context and convey meaning effectively within the platform's constraints. This finding supports Crystal's (2003) and Bodomo's (2009) findings that the emergence of novel language creations and modifications of existing forms demonstrate the creative expression enabled by Facebook. Bodomo (2009) further emphasizes that such linguistic creativity, particularly prevalent among the youth, not only showcases innovation but also reflects the need to keep up with the ever-changing language in the fast-paced world of technology. Furthermore, the observation of language change on social networking sites, as evidenced by new linguistic forms and modifications of existing forms, aligns with the pragmatic notion of language as a dynamic and evolving system.

Participants' posts on Facebook often revolve around personal theme categories such as family, friendship, emotional expression, seeking recommendations, and valuing the opinions of others. These patterns indicate the importance of family and relationships in Filipino culture and highlight the collective nature of Filipino Facebook users. When participants share achievements, family-related content, or greetings for special occasions, they expect positive responses from their FB networks, reinforcing the sense of collectivity or social bonding among other users. Pragmatics acknowledges that cultural factors play a significant role in shaping language use and communication patterns. Thus, understanding the cultural values and norms, such as the importance of family and relationships in this case, provides insights into the motivations and intentions behind participants' language use on Facebook. Moreover, the expectation of positive responses from other FB users when participants share achievements or family-related content reflects the latter's desire for social validation and the sense of collectivity they experience within their Facebook community.

As for communicative purpose, the findings of this study indicate that assertives, or statements expressing a proposition, dominate as the primary communicative purpose on Facebook, which sheds light on the pragmatic intentions of the participants. Student participants' lack of posts about social issues and politics suggests a lack of interest or limited knowledge compared to professional participants, which implies that student participants may have reduced interest or knowledge in these areas. Pragmatics recognizes that social and contextual factors influence individuals' language use, including their interests, knowledge, and motivations. In this case, the lack of political engagement among student participants on Facebook aligns with the pragmatic understanding that individuals prioritize different communicative goals based on their personal preferences and the social dynamics they navigate. As David, San Pascual, and Torres (2019) observe, young citizens often prioritize entertainment over political engagement and demonstrate lower involvement than older citizens. The shifts in speech acts in longer posts demonstrate the pragmatic concept of how a single expression can perform multiple communicative acts simultaneously, thereby reflecting the complexity of language use and the nuanced ways speakers convey meaning in specific contexts.

Facebook likewise afforded users an extension of their offline selves through posting photographs and videos of themselves or with others as well as sharing memes and other content. Participants on the social media platform engage in identity construction by sharing personal experiences, cultural preferences, and opinions. The implicit nature of identity construction aligns with the pragmatic idea that language carries social meaning and that individuals strategically manage their self-presentation to achieve communicative goals. Moreover, participants tend to construct their identities implicitly rather than making explicit statements about themselves which shows that it may be a convenient way of self-disclosure. After all, what better way to tell one's audience that they have such a beautiful voice than by posting a video of themselves singing and getting positive remarks from their Facebook friends? Or when changing one's profile or cover photo, other users 'like' and compliments it? This practice is undoubtedly preferred rather than self-praise, which shows a consensus that humans expect at least some of their wants and needs to be fulfilled by others (Maíz-Arévalo, 2017).

Using humor on Facebook is a positive politeness strategy (Maíz-Arévalo, 2017), fostering social connections and group solidarity (Baym, 1995). Thus, mock-impolite banter among users reveal how their online interactions become an extension and reflection of their offline relationships and boost group solidarity and rapport. Pragmatics recognizes that politeness and humor are essential elements of social interactions, and their presence on the platform highlights their role in online communication.

Few instances of inappropriate behavior on Facebook, such as comments or posts that others find offensive, reflect the pragmatic notion of appropriateness in language use. Users navigate the established norms and expectations of the platform to avoid conflicts and manage interactions proactively, highlighting the need to adhere to social conventions for effective communication. The expectation for Facebook users to behave according to established norms parallels the societal expectations for individuals to follow social norms and be accountable for their behavior. The online environment may provide some anonymity, but the requirement for users to reveal their real names or personal information (Zhao, Grasmuck, & Martin, 2008) suggests that individuals should act responsibly and consider the potential consequences of their actions. Since many interlocutors already have personal relationships in the physical setting, they may strive to maintain them in the virtual realm, which implies that individuals may align their online

behavior with their offline persona to ensure consistency and avoid potential conflict or negative impact on their relationships.

Furthermore, interpersonal behavior is not only dependent on the context and the users but also largely topic-driven (Arendholz, 2013). How individuals express themselves online, such as the words they use and the topics they discuss, can reveal aspects of their identity and personality. Labov (1972) suggested that language choices can reflect social factors like class, ethnicity, age, and gender. Therefore, individuals may consciously or unconsciously project specific identities or personality traits through their online posts and status updates.

In conclusion, these findings highlight the complex interplay between online communication, social norms, interpersonal relationships, communicative goals, and individual identity, emphasizing the importance of context, topic, and participants in shaping the pragmatic aspects of online interactions.

Recommendations

In light of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are proposed.

Social media users should embrace and explore the linguistic innovations and creativity facilitated by Facebook and adapt to the online context by experimenting with changes in capitalization, punctuation, spelling, and abbreviations while ensuring effective communication. Additionally, they should understand the influence of cultural factors on language use. They must develop a sense of responsibility when engaging with social media platforms, mainly when posting status updates, as these can significantly impact both them and others. Since status updates are an extension of one's offline self, social media users should exercise caution and mindfulness regarding the content they share online. Therefore, users must think before they post, considering that their online activity may influence future career opportunities. Maintaining authenticity to foster genuine connections and avoid potential negative consequences associated with misleading portrayals is also crucial.

Teachers should acknowledge the influence of Computer-Mediated Communication (CMC) on language and literacy practices on platforms like Facebook. Familiarity with online language innovations and encouraging their creative use can help bridge linguistic variants between CMC language and standard form, particularly in formal written communication. Moreover, they should encourage their students to reflect on their language use on social media platforms and discuss the pragmatic intentions behind various communicative purposes observed on Facebook. Additionally, teachers can create opportunities for students to critically analyze and discuss the role of social media in shaping language use, identity construction, and social interactions, as well as highlight the importance of being responsible online and adhering to social conventions.

Future researchers can explore various aspects of social media, such as identity construction, utilizing different theoretical frameworks. Investigating online interactions in an anonymous virtual setting, specifically Facebook news sites, focusing on phenomena like flaming and trolling, can provide valuable insights. Lastly, curriculum planners should develop educational programs and instructional materials incorporating digital literacy skills into the curricula that promote pragmatic awareness in online interactions and foster intercultural competence among students. It is also recommended that Codes of Conduct on the use of Facebook be included in these instructional materials.

References:

- Abad, D. A., Marcellana, C. D., & Reboton, G. P. (2016). The Pragmatics of Internet Meme for AB Communication Students of Colegio de San Juan De Letran Calamba. *Ani: Letran Calamba Research Report*, 9-15.
- Abdalhakeem, S. H., & Mubarak, A. (2019). The Humorous Effect of the Inappropriateness of Speech Acts in the Sitcom of "Still Standing". *Dirasat, Human and Social Sciences*, 771-783.
- Abualadas, O. (2020). Shifts in Speech Acts in the Fiction Translation: Evidence of A More Marked Narrational Voice. *Dirasat, Human and Social Sciences*, 61-73.
- AbuSa'aleek, A. O. (2015). Internet Linguistics: A Linguistic Analysis of Electronic Discourse as a New Variety of Language. *International Journal of English Linguistics*, 135-145.
- Adeeb, E. R. (2016). The Net-lingo Abbreviations Delineated in Facebook Language Amongst The Iraqi EFL Learners: A Socio-Pragmatic Analysis. *Diyala Journal*, 621-637.
- AL-Dheleai, Y. M., & Tasir, Z. (2017). Using Facebook for the Purpose of Students' Interaction and Its Correlation with Students' Academic Performance. *The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 170-178.
- Aljasir, S., Bajnaid, A., Elyas, T., & Alnawasrah, M. (2017). Themes of Facebook Status Updates and Levels of Online Disclosure: The Case of University Students. *International Journal of Business Administration*, 80-97.
- Allan, K. (2016). *The Routledge Handbook of Linguistics*. New York: Routledge.
- Almurashi, W. A. (2016). An Introduction to Halliday's Systemic Functional Linguistics. *Journal for the Study of English Linguistics*, 70-80.
- Anglistiky, K. (2014). *Word Formation Process and Usage of Internet Abbreviations in English: A Contrastive View as Regard*. South Bohemia: University of South Bohemia.

- Arendholz, J. (2013). *(In)appropriate Online Behaviorz: A Pragmatic Analysis of Message Board Relations*. Philadelphia: John Benjamins Publishing Company.
- Association, N. J.-O. (2017, August 12). *National Johnson O'Malley Association Elected Voice and Liaison for Programs Nationwide*. Retrieved from <https://www.njoma.com/>: <https://www.njoma.com/home-1.html>
- Austin, J. L. (1962a). *How to Do Things With Words*. Oxford: Clarendon.
- Banuag, L. L. (2018). Code-Switching in Facebook Posts: Episodes of Forms and Reasons. *Graduate School Book of Abstracts*, 12-34.
- Barasa, S. (2010). *Language, Mobile Phones and Internet: A Study of SMS Texting, Email, IM, and SNS Chats in Computer-Mediated Communication (CMC) in Kenya*. Utrecht, The Netherlands: LOT.
- Barash, V., Ducheneaut, N., Isaacs, E., & Belloti, V. (2010). Faceplant: Impression (MIS) Management in Facebook Status Updates. *Proceedings of the Fourth International Conference On Weblogs and Social Media* (pp. 207-210). Washington, DC.: P. Hearst.
- Bauer, L. (1983). *English Word-Formation*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Baumeister, R. F. (1982). Self-esteem, Self-Presentation, and Future Interaction: A Dilemma of Reputation. *Journal of Personality*, 29-45.
- Baumeister, R. F., & Leary, M. R. (1995). The Need to Belong: Desire for Interpersonal Attachments as a Fundamental Human Motivation. *Psychological Bulletin*, 497-529.
- Baym, N. (1995). The Performance of Humor in Computer-Mediated Communication. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*.
- Baym, N. K. (2000). *Tune In, Log On: Soaps, Fandom, and Online Community*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Bennet, J. (2015, February 27). *When Your Punctuation Says it All (!)*. Retrieved from <http://www.nytimes.com>: <https://www.nytimes.com/2015/03/01/style/when-your-punctuation-says-it-all.html>
- Blumler, J. G., & Katz, E. (1974). *The Uses of Mass Communications: Current Perspectives on Gratifications Research*. CA: Sage.
- Bodomo, A. (2009). *Computer Mediated Communication for Linguistics and Literacy: Technology and Natural Language Education*. Hershey: Information Science Publishing.
- Bolander, B., & Locher, M. (2010). Constructing Identity on Facebook: Report on a Pilot Study. In K. Junod, & D. Maillat, *Performing the Self* (pp. 165-185). Tubingen.
- Bridgman, A., Merkley, E., Leowen, P. J., Owen, T., Ruths, D., Teichmann, L., & Oleg, Z. (June 2020). The Causes and Consequences of COVID-19 Misperceptions: Understanding the Role of News and Social Media. *The Harvard Kennedy School Misinformation Review*, 1-18.
- Bucholtz, M., & Hall, K. (2005). Identity and Interaction: A Sociolinguistic Approach. *Discourse Studies*, 585-614.
- Bucholtz, M., & Hall, K. (2005). Identity Interaction: A Sociocultural Linguistic Approach. *Discourse Studies*, 585-614.
- Budaya, P. (2015). Speech Act Analysis of the Main Character in Shrek Movie Script. *Halaman*, 60-64.
- Buechel, E., & Berger, J. (2012, June 18). *Wharton Faculty Platform*. Retrieved from <https://www.wharton.upenn.edu>: https://faculty.wharton.upenn.edu/wp-content/uploads/2012/07/FacebookTherapy_1.pdf
- Caffrey, L. (2017). Social Media and the Construction of Self: How our New Sociotechnical Environment is Changing the Construction of Identity. *Trinity College Library*, 3-133.
- Cameron, D. (1995). *Verbal Hygiene*. London: Routledge.
- Cardente, K. F. (2017). Speech Act Analysis On Facebook Status Updates. *academia.edu*, 20-35.
- Chiucharelli, K. (2011). Social Media and the Problem of Identity. *Marquette University*, 1-8.
- Ciuksys, M. (2021, March 3). *Everything You Need to Know about #Hashtags on Facebook*. Retrieved from <http://www.socialbakers.com>: <https://www.socialbakers.com/blog/1826-everything-you-need-to-know-about-hashtags-on-facebook>
- Crystal, D. (2003). *Language and the Internet*. New York, NY: Cambridge University Press.
- Crystal, D. (2011). *Internet Linguistics*. New York: Routledge.
- Culpeper, J. (1996). Towards and Anatomy of Impoliteness. *Journal of Pragmatics*, 346-367.
- Cutting, J. (2002). *Pragmatics and Discourse*. Canada: Routledge.
- Dalton, E. J. (2013). *Impoliteness in Computer Mediated Communication*. San Diego: San Diego State University.
- Das, A., & Gämback, B. (2013). Code Mixing in Social Media Context: The Last Language Identification Frontier? *TAL*, 41-64.
- Dauphin, P. V. (2018, April 3). *Sarcasm in Relationships*. Retrieved from <http://ccat.sas.upenn.edu>: <http://ccat.sas.upenn.edu/plc/communication/valerie.htm>
- David, C. C., San Pascual, M., & Torres, M. S. (2019). Reliance on Facebook for News and Its Influence in Political Engagement. *PLOS ONE*. Retrieved from PLOS.
- Davies, J. (2007). Display, Identity and the Everyday: Self-Presentation Through Online Image Sharing. *Discourse: Studies in the Cultural Politics of Education*, 549-564.
- Deeran, S. (2013, June 5). *What is Social Media Content Creation?* Retrieved from Huffpost: https://www.huffpost.com/entry/what-is-social-media-cont_b_3383706
- Denti, L., Barbopoulos, I., Nilsson, I., Holmberg, L., Thulin, M., Wendblad, M., . . . Davidsson, E. (2012). *Sweden's Largest Facebook Study*. Göteborg: Gothenberg Research Institute.
- Dictionaries, O. (2013, October 22). *Selfie is named Oxford Dictionaries' Word of the Year 2013*. Retrieved from www.lexico.com: <http://blog.oxforddictionaries.com/press-releases/oxford-dictionaries-word-of-the-year-2013>

- Dijk, T. A. (2009). *Context and Cognition: Knowledge Frames and Speech Act Comprehension*. Barcelona: Cambridge University Press.
- Dino, C. M., & Gustilo, L. E. (2015). Digitalk: An Exploration of the Linguistic Features of CMC. *International Journal of Language, Literature, and Linguistics*, 51-55.
- Directory, G. (2023, January 15). *Speaking to Millennials in Their Language - The Struggle is Real!* Retrieved from <https://www.greenbook.org/>: <https://www.greenbook.org/marketing-research/Speaking-To-Millennials>
- Donnelly, K. (2007, February 2). *Think Before You Click, Site Warns Teenages*. Retrieved from <https://www.independent.ie/>: <https://www.independent.ie/irish-news/think-before-you-click-site-warns-teenagers-26273734.html>
- Dresner, E., & Herring, S. C. (2012). Emoticons and Illocutionary Force. *Communication Theory*, 249-268.
- Drid, T. (2020). A Genre-Based Study of Algerian EFL Writers' Academic Texts: More Structure in Research Article Abstracts. In *Teaching Academic Writing as a Discipline-Specific Skill in Higher Education* (pp. 175-185). Algeria: Kasdi Merbah University.
- Dwivedi, Y., Kapoor, K., & Hsin, C. (2015). Social media marketing and advertising. *The Marketing Review*, 289-309.
- Edwards, J. K. (2015). Shitworde: An Analysis of Linguistic Taboo in the History of the Semantic Field of Excrement. *Purdue University Purdue e-Pubs*, 1-166.
- Filik, R., Turcan, A., Thompson, D., Harvey, N., Davies, H., & Turner, A. (2015). Sarcasm and Emoticons: Comprehension and Emotional Impact. *Quarterly Journal of Experimental Psychology*, 2130-2146.
- Fitzpatrick, N., & Donnelly, R. (2010). Do You See What I Mean? Computer-Mediated Discourse Analysis. In R. Donnelly, J. Harvey, & K. O'Rourke, *Critical Design and Effective Tools for E-Learning in Higher Education: Theory Into Practice* (pp. 1-18). Hershey, PA: Information Science Reference.
- Fleiss, J., Levin, B., & Paik, M. (2003). *Statistical Methods for Rates and Proportions*. New Jersey: Wiley.
- Fontaine, L. (2013). *Analyzing English Grammar: A Systemic Functional Introduction*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Frey, L., Botan, C., & Kreps, G. (1999). *Investigating Communication: An Introduction to Research Methods*. Boston: Allyn & Bacon.
- Fritz, E. (2017). Discourse and Topic. In C. R. Hoffman, & W. Bublitz, *Pragmatics of Social Media* (pp. 275-316). Berlin, Germany: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Fritz, E. (2017). Discourse and Topic. In C. Hoffman, & W. Bublitz, *Pragmatics of Social Media* (pp. 275-307). Berlin: Walter de Gruyter.
- Fung, L., & Carter, R. (2007). Discourse Markers and Spoken English: Nature and Learner Use in Pedagogical Settings. *Applied Linguistics*, 410-439.
- Garbulet, G. (2013). Social Media-- A Pragmatic Approach: Context and Impliucatures . *Procedia--Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 422-426.
- Gerhards, J., & Rucht, D. (1992). Mesomobilization: Organizing and Framing in Two Protest Campaigns in West Germany. *American Journal of Sociology*, 555-596.
- Gervasio, M., & Karuri, M. (2019). Making Identity Through Language in Social Media Discourse by Chuka University Students. *International Journal of Studies in English Language and Literature*, 43-52.
- Globe, Facebook, DepEd Collaborate to Promote Responsible Digital Citizenship in Schools Nationwide. (2018, February 7). Retrieved from <https://technology.inquirer.net/>: <https://technology.inquirer.net/72237/globe-facebook-deped-collaborate-promote-responsible-digital-citizenship-schools-nationwide>
- Goffman, E. (1990 [1959]). *The Presentation of Self in Everyday Life*. London: Penguin.
- Goode, L. (2009). Social News, Citizen Journalism and Democracy. *News Media and Society*, 8-11.
- Graham, S. L. (2017). Politeness and Impoliteness. In C. R. Hoffman, & W. Bublitz, *Pragmatics of Social Media* (pp. 459-491). Berlin: Walter deGruyter.
- Grice, P. H. (1957). Meaning. *Philosophical Review*, 213-223.
- Grosjean, F. (1982). *Life With Two Languages: An Introduction to Bilingualism*. Massachusetts: Harvard University Press.
- Gumperz, J. (1982). *Discourse Strategies*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Gustilo, L. E., & Dino, C. M. (2017). Old Speak or Young Speak: An Analysis of Netspeak Features on Filipino Netspeak . *Advanced Science Letters*, 1-5.
- Halim, N. S., & Maros, M. (2014). The Functions of Code Switching in Facebook Interactions. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 126-133.
- Hallare, K. (2019, June 6). *DICT Proposes Ban on Social Media Use for Classroom Assignments*. Retrieved from <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/>: <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1127535/dict-proposes-ban-on-social-media-use-for-classroom-assignments>
- Halliday, M., & Matthiessen, C. M. (2004). *An Introduction to Functional Grammar*. London: Arnold.
- Hardaker, C. (2010). Trolling in Asynchronous Computer Mediated Communication: From User Discussions to Academic Definitions. *Journal of Politeness Research: Language, Behavior, and Culture*, 215-242.
- Hardaker, C., & McGlashan, M. (2016). Real Men Don't Hate Women: Twitter Rape Threats and Group Identity. *Journal of Pragmatics*, 80-93.
- Hassan, N., & Hashim, A. (2011). Electronic English in Malaysia: Features and Language in Use. *World English*, 551-568.

- Hecht, M. L. (1993). A Research Odyssey: Toward the Development of a Communication Theory of Identity. *Communication Monographs*, 76-82.
- Himmelboim, I., Mc Creery, S., & Smith, M. (2013). Birds of a Feather Tweet Together: Integrating Network and Content Analysis to Examine Cross-Ideology Exposure on Twitter. *Journal of Computer Mediated Communication*, 154-174.
- Hoffman, C. R., & Bublitz, W. (2017). *Pragmatics of Social Media*. Berlin: Walter de Gruyter GmbH.
- Hozhabrossdat, S. (2015). Linguistic identities. How code switching and/ coderossing help constructing solidarity or Otherness in Multilingual Societies. *International Journal of English Literature and Culture*, 194-198.
- HR, R. W. (2018, September 20). *An Analysis of Abbreviation Word Used on Facebook by Seventh Semester Students Of English Department of Iain Bengkulu*. Retrieved from STATE INSTITUTE OF ISLAMIC STUDY (IAIN): <http://repository.iainbengkulu.ac.id/3180/1/THESIS%20RISKI%20WULANDARI%20HR.pdf>
- Huang, J., Thornton, K., & Efthimiadis, E. (2010). Conversational Tagging in Twitter. *21st ACM Conference on Hypertext and Hypermedia* (pp. 173-178). Toronto: ACM.
- Huang, Q. (2014). Facework Strategies in EFL Classroom. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 175-182.
- Hughes, G. (1991). Swearing: A Social History of Foul Language, Oaths and Profanity in English. *Canadian Journal of Linguistics*, 275-278.
- Ibkar, H. F. (2017). *Gender Characteristics in a Conversation on Social Media*. Diponegoro: Diponegoro University. Retrieved from <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/>.
- Ilyas, S., & Khushi, Q. (2012). Facebook Status Updates: A Speech Act Analysis. *Academic Research International*, 500-507.
- Jacob, R. (2017). Genderlect and Dynamics of Communication: A Study on what's app Application User. *The Criterion: An International Journal in English*, 632-650.
- Jacobs, S. W. (2013). *Use of English Word Formation on Facebook*. Manado: Universitas Sam Ratulangi.
- Jacobson, D. (2007). Interpreting Instant Messaging: Context and Meaning in Computer-Mediated Communication. *Journal of Anthropological Research*, 359-381.
- Jay, T. (2000). *Why We Curse: A Neuro-Psychosocial Theory of Speech*. Philadelphia: John Benjamins Publishing.
- Jung, E., & Hecht, M. (2004). Elaborating the Communication Theory of Identity: Identity Gaps and Communication Outcomes. *Communication Quarterly*, 265-283.
- Jurida, S. H., Džanić, M., Pavlović, T., Jahić, A., & Hanić, J. (2016). Netspeak: Linguistic Properties and Aspects of Online Communication in Postponed Time. *Journal of Foreign Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics*, 1-19.
- Kaburise, P. (2012). Recognizing Speech Acts. *A Journal of Language Learning*, 36-48.
- Kaplan, A. M., & Haenlin, M. (2010). Users of the World, unite! The Challenges and Opportunities of Social Media. *Business Horizons*, 59-68.
- Kapranov, O. (2019). Discourse Markers in Writing on Facebook by Early Balanced English/Italian Bilinguals. *Brno Studies in English*, 79-99.
- Kelly, C. (2015). Do You Know What I Mean >:(A Linguistic Study of the Understanding of Emoticons and Emojis in Text Messages. *Halmstad University*, 61-90.
- Khushi, Q., & Ilyas, S. (2012). Facebook Status Updates: A Speech Act Analysis. *Academic Research Journal*, 500-507.
- Koller, M. (1988). *Humour and Society: Explorations in the Sociology of Humour*. Houston, TX: Cap & Gown Press.
- Kreiss, D. (2018). The Networked Self in the Age of Identity Fundamentalism. In *A Networked Self and Platforms, Stories, and Connections* (pp. 12-28). Routledge.
- Labov, W. (1972). *Sociolinguistic Patterns*. Philadelphia, PA: University of Pennsylvania Press.
- Lacamiento, G. M. (2016, July 10). *Netizens Urged: Think Before You Click*. Retrieved from <https://www.philstar.com:https://www.philstar.com/the-freeman/cebu-news/2016/07/10/1601384/netizens-urged-think-you-click>
- Laerd Statistics. (2019, November 29). Retrieved December 2021, from <http://www.statistics.laerd.com:https://statistics.laerd.com/spss-tutorials/fleiss-kappa-in-spss-statistics.php#assumptions-of-fleiss-kappa>
- Lakoff, R. (1975). *Language and Women's Place*. New York: Harper and Row.
- Lampe, C., Ellison, N., & Steinfield, C. (2006). A Face(book) in the Crowd: Social Searching vs. Social Browsing. *Proceedings of the 2006 20th Anniversary Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work* (pp. 160-170). New York, NY: ACM Press.
- Landert, D. (2017). Participation as User Involvement. In C. R. Hoffman, & W. Bublitz, *Pragmatics of Social Media* (pp. 31-59). Berlin, Germany: De Gruyter Muoton.
- Laucuka, A. (2018). Communicative Functions of Hashtags. *Economics and Culture*, 56-62.
- Lee, C. (2014). Language Choice and Self-Presentation in Social Media: The Case of University Students in Hong Kong. In *Language of Social Media* (pp. 91-111).
- Li, L., & Yang, Y. (2018). Pragmatic Functions of Emoji in Internet-Based Communication: A Corpus-Based Study. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Second and Foreign Language Education*, 1-12.
- Lives, F. (2021, July 13). *DIGital Footprints*. Retrieved from <http://www.familylives.org.uk:https://www.familylives.org.uk/advice/your-family/online-safety/digital-footprints/>
- Locher, M., & Watts, R. J. (2005). Politeness Theory and Relational Work. *Journal of Politeness Research*, 9-33.
- Luminet, O., Zech, E., Rimé, B., & Wagner, H. (2000b). Predicting Cognitive and Social Consequences of Emotional Episodes: The Contribution of Emotional Intensity, the Five Factor Model, and Alexithymia. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 471-497.

- M.Torres, J., Collantes, L. M., Astreto, E. T., Millan, A. R., & Gabriel, C. M. (2020). Pandemic Humor: Inventory of the Humor Scripts Produced during the COVID-19 Outbreak. *The Asian EFL Journal*, 138-164.
- Maiz-Arevalo, C. (2017). Getting "liked". In C. R. Hoffman, & W. Bublitz, *Pragmatics of Social Media* (pp. 575-606). Berlin, Germany: Walter de Gruyter GmbH.
- Maíz-Arévalo, C. (2017). Getting "Liked". In C. R. Hoffman, & W. Bublitz, *Pragmatics of Social Media* (pp. 575-606). Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Marketing, U. C. (2023, January 16). *Introduction to Social Media*. Retrieved from University of South Florida: <https://www.usf.edu/ucm/marketing/intro-social-media.aspx>
- Martin, J. (2010). Systemic Functional Linguistic Theory. In *Collected Works of JR Martin*. Shanghai: Shanghai Jiao Tong University Press.
- Maslow, A. (1954). *Motivation and Personality*. New York: Harper.
- Mathiessen, C. M. (2019). register in Systemic Functional Linguistics. *Research Gate*.
- Maurer, D. (2020, February 20). *Slang*. Retrieved from Encyclopedia Britannica: <https://www.britannica.com/topic/slang>
- McCarthy, M., Mathiessen, C., & Slade, D. (2010). *Discourse Analysis*. UK: Press Syndicate of the University of Cambridge.
- McLuhan, M. (1964). *Understanding Media*. Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press.
- Mediyanthi, D. (2012). *A Descriptive Study of Code Mixing in Social Networking (Facebook)*. Salatiga: Islam Studies Salatiga.
- Mey, J. (2004). *Pragmatics: An Introduction*. Oxford: Blackwell Publishing.
- Montes-Alcala, C. (2007). Blogging in Two Languages: Code Switching in Bilingual Blogs. *Selected Proceedings of the 3rd Workshop on Spanish Sociolinguistics* (pp. 162-170). Somerville, MA: Cascadilla Proceeding Project.
- Morris, Charles (1938). *Foundations of the theory of signs*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Mwithi, F., Ndambuki, J., & Nabea, W. (2016). Language and Technology: Linguistic Features of Facebook in Kenya. *Journal of Literature, Language, and Linguistics*, 68-77.
- Myers, D. (2004). *Theories of Emotion*. New York, NY: Worth Publishers.
- Narvas, L. (2017, February 15). *Land of teh Filipinos*. Retrieved September 18, 2017, from <http://www.csun.edu>: <http://www.csun.edu/~lan56728/majorlanguages.htm>
- Nickerson, R. S. (1998). Confirmation Bias: A Ubiquitous Phenomenon in Many Guises. *Review of General Psychology*, 175-230.
- Norrick, N. (1993). *Conversational Joking: Humor in Everyday Talk*. Bloomington, IN: Indiana University Press.
- O'Brien, C. (2022, January 8). *How to Use Hashtags Effectively on Social Media*. Retrieved from Digital Marketing Institute: <https://digitalmarketinginstitute.com/blog/how-to-use-hashtags-in-social-media#:~:text=A%20hashtag%20is%20a%20word,your%20posts%20and%20encourage%20interaction.>
- Ovadia, S. (2009). Exploring the Potential of Twitter as a Research Tool. *Behavioral and Social Sciences Librarian*, 202-205.
- Palacio, M. A., & Gustilo, L. (2016). A Pragmatic Analysis of Discourse Particles in Filipino Computer-Mediated Communication. *Gema Online Journal of Language*, 1-20.
- Pazzanese, C. (2015, July 2015). *The Harvard Gazette*. Retrieved from news.harvard.edu: <https://news.harvard.edu/gazette/story/2015/07/go-ahead-be-sarcastic/>
- Pebrianto, M., Latifani, H., & Awaliyah, D. (2018). Types of Speech Acts Used on Instagram Comments of Ellen Degeneres' Account. *Seminar Nasional Struktural*, 210-218.
- Pihlaja, S., & Musloff, A. (2017). Discourse and Ideology. In C. R. Hoffmann, & W. Bublitz, *Prde Gruyteragmatics of Social Media* (pp. 381-403). Berlin, Germany: Walter de Gruyter GmbH .
- Placencia, M. E., & Lower, A. (2017). Compliments and Compliment Responses. In C. R. Hoffman, & W. Bublitz, *Pragmatics of Social Media* (pp. 633-660). Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Post, W. (2011, September 1). *Digital Publishing Guidelines*. Retrieved from www.washingtonpost.com: <http://www.washingtonpost.com/wp-srv/guidelines/social-media.html>
- Randolph, J. J. (2005). Free-Marginal Multirater Kappa (Multirater k free): An Alternative to Fleiss' Fixed-Marginal Multi-rater Kappa. *Joensu Learning and Instruction Symposium*, (pp. 1-30). Joensu, Finland.
- Rappler. (2017, January 30). *PH Spends Most Time Online and on Social Media-Report*. Retrieved from <https://www.rappler.com>: <https://www.rappler.com/technology/features/159720-ph-spends-most-time-online-and-on-social-media-report>
- Responsibility, C. f. (2017, January 3). *Knowing Your Source: Think Before You Click*. Retrieved from cmfr-phil.org: <http://cmfr-phil.org/in-context/knowning-your-source-think-before-you-click/>
- Riana, R. D. (2018). A Sociolinguistic Study on the Use of Code Mixing in Instagram by the Students of English Education Department at IAIN Salatiga. *State Institue for Islamic Studies*, 1-105.
- Rogers, J. (2019). The Use of Social Media and Its Impact for Research. *BioRes*, 5022-5024.
- Rules of Conduct*. (2010). Retrieved from Twitch.tv: <https://twitch.tv/p/rules-of-conduct>
- Sampietro, A. (2016). Exploring the Punctuating Effect of Emoji in Spanish Whatsapp Chats. *Lenguas Modernas*, 91-113.

- Schiffrin, D. (1987). *Discourse Markers*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Scott, M. (2017, October 13). *What's the Psychology Behind Being Nosy?* Retrieved from <https://www.quora.com:https://www.quora.com/Whats-the-psychology-behind-being-nosy>
- Seargeant, P., & Tagg, C. (2014). *The Language of Social Media: identity and Community on the Internet*. New York: Palgrave McMillan.
- Seibel, B. (2019). Insta-Identity: The Construction of Identity Through Instagram an Extended Literature Review. *Portland State University PDX Scholar*, 1-26.
- Serafica, R. (2017, May 24). *How to Be a Responsible Netizen? Keep Calm and Think Before You Click*. Retrieved from <https://www.rappler.com:https://www.rappler.com/move-ph/170798-think-before-click-social-media-crisis>
- Shanahan, N., Brennan, C., & House, A. (2019). Self-harm and Social Media: Thematic Analysis of Images Posted on Three Social Media Sites. *BMJ Open*, 1-6.
- Shea, V. (1994, May 15). *Netiquette*. Retrieved from <http://www.mccc.edu:https://www.mccc.edu/~virtcoll/Netiquette.pdf>
- Shumaker, C., Loranger, D., & Dorie, A. (2017). Dressing for the Internet: A Study of Female Self-Presentation Via Dress on Instagram. *Fashion, Style & Popular Culture*, 365-382.
- Simon, S., & Dejica-Cartis, D. (2014). Speech Acts in Writtem Advertisements: Identification, Classification and Analysis. *Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 234-239.
- Smolowe, J. (1995). Intimate Strangers. *Time*(145), pp. 20-21.
- Spencer-Oatey, H., & Zegarac, V. (2010). *Pragmatics*. UK: Press Syndicate of the University of Cambridge.
- SunStar. (2017, August 6). *Shookt. SMH*. Retrieved from www.sunstar.com.ph:https://www.sunstar.com.ph/article/157085/shookt-smh
- Tafesse, W., & Wien, A. (2017). A Framework for Categorizing Social Media Posts. *Cogent Business & Management* , 1-22.
- Tannen, D. (1990). *You Just Don't Understand*. New York: Ballantine.
- Tarroja, M. C. (2010). Revisiting the Definition and Concept of Filipino Family: A Psychological Perspective. *Philippine Journal of Psychology*, 177-193.
- Thompson, R. (2018, April 02). *Millenials Destroyed the Rules of Written English-- and Created Something Better*. Retrieved from <http://www.mashable.com:mashable.com/2018/04/02/millennials-written-english/>
- Totanesis, B. C., & Ballesteros- Lintao, R. (2019). Textese Categories and Textese Application In L2 Class Discussion. *i-manager's Journal on English Language Teaching*, 14-31.
- Trifonas, P. P. (2015). *Internet Handbook of Semiotics*. Toronto, Canada: Springer.
- Tsehelska, M. (2016). Teaching Politically Correct Language. *English Teaching Forum*, 20-32.
- Uzuegbunam, C. E. (2013, October 7). *The Social Responsibility Theory of the Press: A Contemporary Review*. Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu:https://www.academia.edu/11187397/The_social_responsibility_theory_A_contemporary_review
- Vaismoradi, M., Turunen, H., & Bondas, T. (2013, March 11). *Content analysis and thematic analysis: Implications for Conducting a Qualitative Descriptive Study*. Retrieved from <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/:https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/nhs.12048#:~:targetText=Content%20analysis%20uses%20a%20descriptive,Braun%20%26%20Clarke%2C%202006>.
- Vandergriff, I. (2013). Emotive Communication Online: A Contextual Analysis of Computer-Mediated Communication (CMC). *Journal of Pragmatics*, 1-12.
- VanDijck, J. (2008). Digital Photography: Communication, Identity, Memory. *Visual Communication*, 57-76.
- VanHouse, N. (2009). Collocated Photo Sharing, Story-Telling, and the Performance of Self. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, 1073-1086.
- Vegh, S. (2003). Classifying Forms of Online Activism. In M. MacCaughey, & M. Ayers, *Cyberactivism: Online Activism in Theory and Practice* (pp. 71-95). New York, NY: Routledge.
- Velasco, J. (2020). Millennials as Digital Natives: Examining the Social Media Activities of the Philippine Y-Generation. *Pertanika Journal of Social Science and Humanities*, 1940-1957.
- Walther, J. B., Liang, Y., DeAndrea, D. C., Tong, S., Spottswood, E. L., & Amichai-Hamburger, Y. (2011). The Effect of Feedback on Identity Shift in Computer-Mediated Communication. *Media Psychology*, 1-26.
- Weir, K. (2012, November). *The Pain of Social Rejection*. Retrieved September 10, 2019, from <http://www.apa.org:http://www.apa.org/monitor/2012/04/rejection.aspx>
- Werny, A. (2013). Taboo Lexeme Conditioning and Obscenities in American English. *Digital Commons@EMU*, 450-453.
- Wihbey, J. (2013, March 15). *The Journalist's Resource*. Retrieved from <https://journalistsresource.org:https://journalistsresource.org/economics/research-internet-effects-politics-key-studies/>
- Wikström, P. (2014). #srynotfunny: Communicative Functions of Hashtags on Twitter. *SKY Journal of Linguistics*, 127-152.
- Williams, D. L. (2013, June). *Why People Use Social Media: A Uses and Gratifications Approach*. Retrieved from ResearchGate.net: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/237566776>
- Winter, S., Neubaum, G., Eimler, S., Gordon V., Theil, J., Hermann, J., . . . Krämer, N. C. (2014). Another Brick in the Facebook Wall: How Personality Traits Relate to the Content of Status Updates. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 194-202.
- Wu, Y. Q. (2018). The Linguistic and Non-linguistic Features in Facebook Status Updates Among Malaysian Youths: A Sociolinguistic Perspective. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Sciences*, 247-253.

- Yanagihara, Y. (2007). A Study of Bilingual Education in the Philippines: Difference in Pupil's Degree of Understanding Between Learning Mathematics in Cebuano and English. *The Keiai Journal of International Studies*, 175-201.
- Yunis, M. A. (2019). Language of Social Media: An Investigation of the Changes That Soft Media Has Imposed on Language Use. *9th International Research Conference on Education, Language and Literature* (pp. 308-315). Azerbaijan: Khazar University.
- Zappavigna, M. (2012). *Discourse of Twitter and Social Media*. New York, NY: Continuum International Publishing Group.
- Zappavigna, M. (2015). Searchable Talk: The Linguistic Functions of Hashtags. *Social Semiotics*, 274-291.
- Zappavigna, M. M. (2015). Searchable Talk: The Linguistic Functions of Hashtags. *Social Semiotics*, 274-291.
- Zentella, A. (1997). *Growing Up Bilingual: Puerto Rican Children in New York*. Malden: Blackwell Publishers.
- Zhao, S. (2006). Cyber-Gathering Places and Online-Embedded Relationships. *Annual Meetings of the Eastern Sociological Society in Boston*. Boston.
- Zhao, S., Grasmuck, S., & Martin, J. (2008). Identity Construction on Facebook: Digital Empowerment in Achored Relationships. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 1816-1836.
- Zitzen, M. (2004). *Establishing Topical Coherence in Electronic Communications: A Corpus-Based Analysis of Metadiscursive Topic Shift Markers in Asynchronous and Synchronous Computer-Mediated Communication (CMC)*. Stuttgart, Germany: Ibidem-Verlag.
- Zuckerberg, M. (2009, June). The Wired Interview: Facebook's Mark Zuckerberg. (F. Vogelstein, Interviewer)
- Zumaroh, S. (2008). The Analysis of Speech Act Used in "Air Force One" Movie Script. *State Institute for Islamic Studies*, 1-69.